

Aneta Skalec

**P. CAIR. CAT. 10368:
A FRAGMENTARY AGORANOMIC SALE
FROM PATHYRIS**

THE PAPYRUS EDITED IN THIS PAPER,¹ was discovered in Pathyris (modern Gebelein), a Ptolemaic town located about 30 km to the southwest of Luxor, on the western bank of the Nile in Upper Egypt.² It was described by Bernard P. Grenfell and Arthur S. Hunt in their catalogue of Greek papyri from Cairo.³ In the introduction to this volume, the authors indicated that a few late Ptolemaic documents from

¹ This papyrus was edited in M. Kashaf's 1997 Ain Shams dissertation (no. 5, pp. 38–46; see U. GAD, *A Checklist of the Egyptian Museum's Unpublished Greek Papyri*, Cairo 2016, p. 5). Unfortunately, I could not consult this dissertation and check the original editor's readings. I contacted professor Noha Salem from Ain Shams University for a copy of Kashaf's PhD. However, she failed to find it in both the faculty and the central library. I would like to express my sincere gratitude to professor Noha Salem for her help.

I studied the papyrus from images kindly provided on behalf of the Egyptian Museum in Cairo by Wojciech Ejsmond, who personally supervised the taking of the photographs. Therefore, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to him for his irreplaceable help and to the Egyptian Museum for their permission to publish the document. My thanks go also to Marcin Kotyl and an anonymous reviewer for their elaborate comments on the earlier draft of this paper. Their feedback has proven to be most helpful.

² W. EJSMOND, A. SKALEC, & J. M. CHYLA, 'The topography of the town of Pathyris in the light of the current research', [in:] *PapCongr.* XXIX, p. 331.

³ B. P. GRENFELL & A. S. HUNT, *Greek Papyri: Catalogue général des antiquités égyptiennes du Musée du Caire, Nos. 10001–10869*, Oxford 1903, no. 10368.

Gebelein, including the aforementioned papyrus, were part of the Cairo Museum collection already before the year 1897. Moreover, they stated that these documents belonged to the same find as those published in *P. Grenf.* I and II.⁴ Unfortunately, there is no additional information identifying the person of the finder or the precise date of the discovery.

The image (fig. 1) shows a light-brown fragment in three pieces. Between the sheets two and three, a small piece of papyrus is missing, containing one to three letters. Two columns of the text seem to have been written in two different hands (as in some other agoranomic contracts, although it is not always easy to decide whether the hand is different or just written more quickly and cursive⁵). The first column (4.8 cm in width) is written in small and rapid cursive hand; the second column (19.5 cm in width) in upright and neat cursive hand. Both the first and the second hands of the discussed document are extremely similar to the one found in *P. Batav.* 6 (Pathyris, 110 BC).⁶ It can be seen especially in the specific writing of *Ἀλεξάνδρου* and the final *nu*. Also Pestman, in his edition of *P. Batav.* 6, had the impression that the document had been written in two different hands.⁷ However, we need to remember that in general the hands in the agoranomic documents do not differ much from one another.⁸

The text runs along the fibres. The margins of the papyrus are preserved on the left and upper sides. Below, a substantial portion must be lost. The overall length of what remains, as well as the fact that the right margin is not preserved, makes it impossible to determine whether there may have been a third column in the present text or not.

The papyrus is mounted on beige card paper, which implies that no writing would have been visible on the back. It bears the note 'Gebelein'

⁴ GRENFELL & HUNT, *Greek Papyri* (cit. n. 3), p. vii.

⁵ M. VIERROS, *Bilingual Notaries in Hellenistic Egypt. A Study of Greek as a Second Language*, Brussels 2012, p. 74; P. W. PESTMAN, 'Agoranomoi et actes agoranomiques: Krokodilopolis et Pathyris, 145-88 av. J.-C.', [in:] IDEM (ed.), *Textes et études de papyrologie grecque, démotique et copte* [= *Papyrologica Lugduno-Batava* 23], Leiden 1985, p. 34; *P. Batav.*, p. 56.

⁶ See the photo online at <<https://berlpap.smb.museum/02578/>> (accessed 10 January 2022).

⁷ *P. Batav.*, p. 56.

⁸ VIERROS, *Bilingual Notaries* (cit. n. 5), p. 91; PESTMAN, 'Agoranomoi' (cit. n. 5), p. 34.

in pencil and the inventory numbers of the papyrus. The papyri found in modern Gebelein were written not only in Pathyris but also in Krokodilopolis (whose precise location in the Greco-Roman times is unknown⁹). However, almost all Krokodilopolis' contracts concern the inhabitants of Pathyris.¹⁰ Certain linguistic features suggest that the document in question was indeed written in Pathyris.

The papyrus contains a fragmentary preserved agoranomic contract of sale.¹¹ The first column, which contains a summary of the contents of the contract in five lines (the so-called *scriptura interior*), is complete; of the full contract in the second column (the so-called *scriptura exterior*) six lines of the dating formula are preserved. The *scriptura interior* consisted normally of a short date and a summary of the contents of the contract, and all those elements are preserved in the papyrus under discussion. The *scriptura exterior* usually encompassed the protocol, contract proper, and signature of the *agoranomos*.¹² The protocol had a form of one sentence including the dating formula, the place of writing, and the name of the *agoranomos*. In the *scriptura exterior*, after the dating formula, there would be a detailed description of the seller and the sold object together with its location and neighbours. After this, the name of the buyer, the sum paid for the purchase, the clause concerning previous ownership and warranty, as well as the final signature of the *agoranomos* would have followed.¹³ None of these is preserved. Sometimes such documents contain a receipt for the tax on sales (*ἐγκύκλιον*), but not always.¹⁴

⁹ EJSMOND, SKALEC, & CHYLA, 'The topography' (cit. n. 2), p. 332 n. 1.

¹⁰ PESTMAN, 'Agoranomoi' (cit. n. 5), p. 10.

¹¹ On the format of agronomic acts, see PESTMAN, 'Agoranomoi' (cit. n. 5), pp. 33–44; VIERROS, *Bilingual Notaries* (cit. n. 5), pp. 74–76.

¹² VIERROS, *Bilingual Notaries* (cit. n. 5), p. 75; PESTMAN, 'Agoranomoi' (cit. n. 5), pp. 33–34.

¹³ J. M. S. COWEY, 'VBP II 10 and P. Lond. III 682 reassembled', *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik* 120 (1998), p. 160.

¹⁴ See PESTMAN, 'Agoranomoi' (cit. n. 5), pp. 37–39; P. W. PESTMAN, 'Ἰμπότ ἐγκύκλιον à Pathyris et à Krokodilopolis', [in:] E. BOSWINKEL & P. W. PESTMAN (eds.), *Textes grecs, démotiques et bilingues [= Papyrologica Lugduno-Batava 19]*, Leiden 1978, pp. 214–222.

col. i

(hand 2) (ἔτους) δ Μεχείρ δ

ἀπέδοτο Χολῶς Σάμιος

πή(χαις) ιγ ζ ἔμβαδοῦ

4 ἐπρίατο Πατήης Πύρου

χα(λκοῦ) β

col. ii

(hand 1) βασιλευόντων βασιλίσης καὶ βασιλέως Πτολεμα[ί]ου
θεῶν Φιλομητό[ρ]ων Σωτήρων

ἔτους δ ἐφ ἱερείως βασιλέως Πτολεμαίου θεοῦ Φιλομήτορος

Σω[τῆ]ρος Ἀλεξάνδρ(ο)υ

καὶ θεῶν Σωτήρων καὶ θεῶν Ἀδε[λφ]ῶν καὶ θεῶν Εὐεργετῶν

κα[ὶ θε]ῶν Φιλοπατ(ό)ρων

4 καὶ θεῶν Ἐπιφ[α]νῶν καὶ θ[εοῦ] Εὐ[πάτο]ρος καὶ θεοῦ

Φιλ[ο]μήτορος κ[αὶ θ]εοῦ Φιλοπά-

τορος ν[ε]ῖ[ου] καὶ θε[οῦ] Εὐε[ρ]γ[έτ]ου κα[ὶ θεῶ]ν Φιλομητ[ό]ρων

Σωτήρων, ἱεροῦ πώλου

Ἰσιδ[ος], μεγάλης μητ[ρ]ὸς θεῶν, ἀθλοφόρου Βερενίκ[ης]

Εὐεργέτιδος, καν[η]φόρου

i.1. δ pap. || i.2 l. Σαμίου || i.3 π⁹ pap. || i.5 χ⁰ pap. || ii.2. l. ἱερέως

In year 4, Mecheir 4, Cholos son of Samios sold 13 1/2 square cubits. Pateus son of Pyros bought for 2,000 copper (drachmae).

In the 4th year of the reign of the Queen and King Ptolemy, gods Philometores and Soteris, in the priesthood of King Ptolemy god Philometor Soter as the priest of Alexander, and the gods Soteris, and the gods Adelphoi, and the gods Euergetai, and the gods Philopatores, and the gods Epiphaneis, and the god Eupator, and the god Philometor, and the god Philopator Neos, and the god Euergetes, and the gods Philometores Soteris, and of the Sacred Foal of Isis, the great mother of the gods, and of the Prize-Bearer of Berenike Euergetis and the Basket-Bearer [---]

Fragmentary papyrus scroll with several columns of ancient Egyptian hieroglyphs. The text is heavily damaged and partially illegible. The fragments are arranged in a roughly horizontal line, showing the original layout of the scroll. The hieroglyphs are arranged in vertical columns, with some characters appearing to be in a different script or dialect than others, possibly indicating a mix of languages or a specific dialect.

Fig. 1. Papyrus *P. Cair.* 10368. © The Egyptian Museum in Cairo

Col. i

1. The date here corresponds to 18 February 113 BC. The daily date in the text is a bit problematic. What I see here is a *delta* open from the top corner, unlike the one found in the year date. Such an open *delta* is, however, clearly visible also in the word ἀπέδοτο and is common with some scribes from Pathyris (e.g. *P. Lond.* III 881 [108 BC]; Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* [cit. n. 5], p. 95). What raises some doubts is the stroke protruding to the right, which one would expect in a combination of letters. However, this particular form of *delta*, with the projecting stroke, can be seen also in the dating formula in *scriptura exterior* (l. 2) in the discussed papyrus, and *P. Lond.* III 880, l. 1, dated to the same year (15 March 113 BC).

As our document dates to 113 BC, it was almost certainly written under the *agoranomos* Heliodoros, who appears as the main *agoranomos* in the documents from Krokodilopolis and Pathyris in the years 124–112 BC (the main office was in Krokodilopolis, with that in Pathyris being only a branch where the name of the main notary would always be mentioned in texts as well: Pestman, ‘Agoranomoi’ [cit. n. 5], p. 10; Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* [cit. n. 5], p. 82). The document might have been written directly under his supervision in Pathyris, as Heliodoros is quite often found there, where he himself drew up a series of contracts (Pestman, ‘Agoranomoi’ [cit. n. 5], p. 11). It might have also been signed by one of the subordinate *agoranomoi* operating directly in Pathyris under Heliodoros – the first of those was Areios (131–113 BC), followed by Ammonios (113–109 BC); see Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* (cit. n. 5), p. 83. The year 113 BC was a time of transition between the two in the Pathyris office (Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* [cit. n. 5], p. 91). It is impossible to indicate which of them is more likely, as both appear in documents from the same day, namely 15 March 113 BC, a month later than the discussed papyrus: Areios in *P. Lond.* III 1203, Ammonios in *P. Strash.* II 85. On these two individuals, see P. W. Pestman, ‘Agoranomie: un avant-poste de l’administration grecque enlevé par les Égyptiens?’, [in:] H. Maehler & V. Strocka (eds.), *Das ptolemäische Ägypten: Akten des internationalen Symposions, 27.–29. September 1976 in Berlin*, Mainz am Rhein 1978, pp. 208–209; Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* (cit. n. 5), pp. 84–85; G. Fogolari, ‘Gli “agoranomi” di Pathyris-Crocodilopoli (Tebaide)’, *Aegyptus* 3/4 (1921), pp. 334–335.

2. Χολῶς: It might be either an Egyptian name Χο(λ)λῶς, -ῶτος or a quite rare variant (TM NamVar 15348) of a more commonly-found Greek name Χῶλος, -ου (TM Nam 2635). According to Trismegistos the form Χολῶς is attested sixteen times for eight individuals in documents dating from the third century BC to the second century AD, usually of Fayumic provenance. The variant Χολλῶς (TM NamVar 15345) is attested nine times, also for eight individuals, in documents dating from the first to the fourth century AD. In most cases it occurs in Thebes. Until now, this name has not been confirmed in the papyri from Pathyris, but its reading does not raise any doubts.

Σάμιος: It can be interpreted in two ways, as either an ethnic designation or a patronymic. Σάμιος (man of Samos) is an ethnic designation rarely attested in Egypt. According to C. A. La'da, *Foreign Ethnicities in Hellenistic Egypt*, Leuven 2002, pp. 281–282, it occurs thirteen times, usually in Lower Egypt or the Fayum. So far it has not been confirmed in documents from Pathyris. However, even if the interpretation of Samios as the ethnic designation is very tempting, it seems fairly unlikely. In the *scriptura interior* of other agoranomic documents from Pathyris, only the names of the seller and the buyer are indicated, often with the patronymic, but never with the ethnic designation. The last element appears in the *scriptura exterior*, but the part containing it, unfortunately, has not survived in the discussed document.

Because of the above-mentioned reasons, it seems much more likely that Σάμιος in the papyrus is a patronymic, although the name Σάμιος (TM Nam 23287) is very rare, being papyrologically attested only twice: *P. Tebt.* III 722, i, l. 1 (Arsinoites, 199–175? BC) and *BGU* I 46, iii, l. 3 (Krokodilopolis [Arsinoites], AD 193). However, the writing is clear. Such an interpretation requires assuming that the scribe mistakenly wrote the name in the nominative instead of the genitive, as the name unequivocally ends with a *sigma*. Even if this is quite a rare mistake – usually the patronymics are systematically formed – we find examples of such mistakes also in other documents from Pathyris (Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* [cit. n. 5], p. 163). This may be explained in two ways. Firstly, it is possible that the genitive ending was confounded with the nominative one, as the nominative singular of the second declension masculine has the same ending as the third declension genitive (Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* [cit. n. 5], pp. 140, 158–159, 163). Σάμιος belongs to the second declension, of which genitive would be Σαμίου. It can be that the writer thought that the ending *-os* indicated the genitive even though in the second declension the word Σάμιος marks the nominative (Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* [cit. n. 5], pp. 158–159). The second explanation might be the confusing usage of the endings *-is* / *-ios* of the names ending in *-is* in the nominative. The nominative is sometimes used for the genitive, and the genitive (*-ios*) is sometimes used in place of the nominative. It must be remembered that the ending *-os* is a very common nominative ending in masculine nouns (second declension). Thus, taking that into account, it is not very surprising that it might have been confused with the genitive *-ios* (Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* [cit. n. 5], p. 170).

It cannot be completely ruled out either that the name in question would be Σάμις, *-ios*, declined like, for instance, the Theban name Πέρμαμις, Περμάμιος. However, such a name is not attested papyrologically.

3. ἐμβαδοῦ: ἐμβαδόν has a double meaning, ‘surface, area’ or, as an adjective, ‘square’ (LSJ, *s.v.*). This term is quite uncommon and among other documents from Pathyris appears only in two of Dryton’s wills, which contain the formula πῆ(χρεις) ἐμβαδοῦς δ εἰς κλιβάνου τόπον, ‘4 square cubits for the site of an oven’:

P. Dryton 3, l. 24 (126 BC), where it is reconstructed, and *P. Dryton* 4, l. 14 (126 BC).¹⁵ In addition, for the Ptolemaic period the term is also attested in *P. Enteux*. 66 (Magdola, 218 BC), ll. 9–10: *πήχεις ἑβδομήκοντα κ[ατ'] ἔμβαδόν*, ‘seventy square cubits’, indicating a measure of a piece of *ψιλὸς τόπος*, ‘building ground’, occupied against the contract by Theodosios, and in *SB XXIV* 15973 (unknown provenance, 132 BC), l. 4: *μὴ τασσομένωι ἔμβαδόν*, ‘not to pay tax’. In the first three documents, *ἔμβαδόν* clearly occurs in connection with a measure of area. In the last one, it is interpreted by Kramer as a synonym to *ἔμβαδικόν*, that is a tax paid by land tenants (B. Kramer, ‘Der *κτίστης* Boethos und die Einrichtung einer neuen Stadt. Teil I. P. UB Trier’, *Archiv für Papyrusforschung* 43 [1997], p. 325). In Roman times, this term was also used to denote an area (eg., *SB XIV* 11878 + *P. Vindob. G* 59.529 [unknown provenance, 2nd cent. AD]). Given that in the discussed document it appears in connection with the word *πήχεις*, it almost certainly refers to such measurement. It seems probable that the correct version here would be a reversed word order, namely *πή(χεις) ἔμβαδοῦ γ λ*. It cannot be excluded that the scribe added *ἔμβαδοῦ* after the number of cubits on second thought, having realised that he had forgotten it. Then the phrase might be translated as ‘square cubits’. If, however, *ἔμβαδοῦ* was intentionally placed after the number, it might be translated as ‘of area’ (see a similar phrase in demotic *P. Ryl. Dem.* 23, l. 3 [Pathyris, 115–108 BC]). Regardless of the translation, *ἔμβαδόν* refers to a measure, most probably corresponding to the demotic *mḥḥt*, ‘square cubit’, measuring about 0.275 m² (*CDD, M*, pp. 190–191; S. P. Vleeming, ‘Demotic measures of length and surface, chiefly in the Ptolemaic period’, [in:] Pestman [ed.], *Textes et études* [cit. n. 5] p. 213 n. 42). It should be clearly distinguished from *πήχυσ στερεός*, occurring more often in documents from Pathyris and Thebaid. A *πήχυσ στερεός* was ground or standard cubit, equivalent to 100 square cubits (*ἔμβαδόν* in the discussed document), demotic *mḥ-itn*, which means 1 standard cubit amounts to 1/100 aoura = 27.56 m² (Kramer, ‘Der *κτίστης*’ [cit. above], p. 337; *CDD, M*, p. 186; Vleeming, ‘Demotic measures’ [cit. above], p. 221, § 16).

Therefore, the property addressed in *P. Cair. Cat.* 10368 measured merely 3.7125 m². As such, it was quite small. Except for the dimensions, the *scriptura interior* does not provide any details on the object of sale. This would be pointed out in the *scriptura exterior*, which was not preserved. Hence, it is unknown what kind of property was involved. One can practically exclude the sale of a house or arable land, as in such cases within the Pathyris documentation the sold item would always be indicated in the *scriptura interior*. Only in *ψιλὸς τόπος* sales, the exact object of the contract was not usually defined in the *scriptura interior*, being reduced only to the specification of the number of cubits. However, in these

¹⁵ Translation after K. VANDORPE, *The Bilingual Family Archive of Dryton, his Wife Apollonia and their Daughter Senmouthis*, Brussels 2002, p. 85.

cases, *πήχυς στερεός* was always used as a unit of measure (*P. Grenf.* I 25 [114 BC]; *P. Strasb.* II 85 [113 BC]; *BGU* III 994 [113 BC]; *P. Strasb.* II 86 [111 BC]; see K. Maresch, *Bronze und Silber. Papyrologische Beiträge zur Geschichte der Währung im ptolemäischen und römischen Ägypten bis zum 2. Jahrhundert n. Chr.* [= *Abhandlungen der Nordrhein-Westfälischen Akademie der Wissenschaften* 25], Wiesbaden 1996, pp. 207–208). In the period in which the document under discussion was written, the usual price for one standard cubit of *ψιλὸς τόπος* was 1,000 drachmae. In *P. Cair. Cat.* 10368, the price is, however, much lower. Taking all of the above into account, it should be assumed that the papyrus refers to a different type of property. Looking at other documents from the Ptolemaic period, it seems likely that this could have involved some unusual use of a small portion of land, such as in *P. Dryton* 3 and 4 – a site of an oven, or *P. Enteux.* 66 – a long and narrow part of a *ψιλὸς τόπος*.

4. *Πατήυς*: Grenfell and Hunt pointed out that the name of the buyer was Pates (*P. Cair. Cat.*, p. 48), which is a common name attested in Pathyris (*Πατήυς*: TM Nam 772). However, in my opinion, between the *eta* and the final *sigma* there is an additional letter, namely an *upsilon*. Therefore, the name in question should be read *Πατήυς*. The same writing is confirmed papyrologically only once, in *P. Corn.* 21, l. 177 (Philadelphia, AD 33). However, this document contains the patronymic in the genitive (*Ἀτρῆς Πατήυς*). According to Trismegistos, the name in question (TM NamVar 3568) would thus be a variant of *Πατήυς*, which seems plausible, as in Roman times the genitive form of this name was often *Πατήους*: for example *O. Bodl.* II 474 (Thebes, AD 41); *O. Strasb.* I 260 (Thebaid, AD 23). In the case of *P. Cair. Cat.* 10368, however, the situation is different, because the buyer's name occurs in the nominative. Since the transcription of this Egyptian name from *Pa-tw* as *Πατήυς* is well-established in documents written in Pathyris and Krokodilopolis, and there is no exemption from this writing there, it seems unlikely to me that the buyer's name is a variant of *Πατήυς*. In my opinion, it is much more likely to see it as a variant of the name *Πατεύς* (TM Nam 4946). Checking other names with the ending *-ηυς* in the nominative revealed that it generally occurred in transcriptions of Egyptian names whose standard Greek version ended in *-εϋς*. Such a phenomenon is attested only twice in the Ptolemaic period (*UPZ* I 98 [Memphis, 158 BC], v^o, l. 98: *Ἀμονμηϋς* [TM NamVar 67051] < *Ἀμενεϋς* [TM Nam 34]; *P. Ryl.* II 72 [Arsinoite, BC 99–98], ll. 98: *Σοκῆυς* [TM NamVar 43445] < *Σοκεϋς* [TM Nam 1129] and 103: *Θοτῆυς* [TM NamVar 10089] < *Θοϋς* [TM Nam 1388]) and slightly more often in the Roman times (e.g. *PSI* VIII 901 [Tebtynis, AD 46], ll. 8: *Πανομηϋς* [TM NamVar 43510] < *Πανομειϋς* [TM Nam 735] and 19: *Ὀρσεηϋς* [TM NamVar 43488] < *Ὀρσεϋς* [TM Nam 569]; *O. Ashm.* 79 [unknown provenance, 3rd cent. AD?], ll. 4 and 7: *Χεμπνηϋς* [TM NamVar 43451] < *Χεμπσεϋς* [TM Nam 121]; *P. Corn.* 18 [Oxyrhynchus, AD 291], l. 29: *Ταῆυς* [TM NamVar 43495] < *Ταεϋς* [TM Nam 6012]). These are rare cases, which likely occurred, because the opposition between the long and short vowels

probably did not exist in Egyptian (A. I. Blasco Torres, *Representing Foreign Sounds. Greek Transcriptions of Egyptian Anthroponyms from 800 BC to 800 AD*, Leuven 2017, p. 606). Πατεῦς is papyrologically attested only eleven times for ten individuals from 175 BC to AD 317, never in Pathyris. However, its variants are quite similar to the one found in the discussed text: Πατηεῦς (TM NamVar 12556; BGU XVI 2673, iii, l. 88 [Herakleopolites, 25–1 BC]), Πατηοῦς (TM NamVar 12557; O. Heid. 396, l. 5 [Arsinoites, 2nd half of the 2nd cent. AD]).

Πύρου: Πύρος (TM NamVar 13523) is a variant of a much more common name Πύρρος (TM Nam 5381), confirmed in Trismegistos twenty-nine times for eighteen individuals, in the period from 332 BC to AD 295. However, it never appeared in Pathyris. The clearest letter of the name is the *rho*, followed by the *omicron* and the *upsilon*. The two last letters are analogous to their writing in ἐμβαδοῦ in the preceding line, with the final stroke of the *upsilon* strongly elongated. The beginning of the name is somehow awkward, especially because of the quite atypical *sigma* of the preceding name. There are three hooks which might be both *pi-upsilon*, *upsilon-pi*, but also *tau-eta*. The second possibility can be excluded, as in Trismegistos there is no name beginning with those letters. The most likely seems to be the first option and, actually, the only name that corresponds to these letters is Πύρος. However, it cannot be ruled out for the discussed document that the name is Τήρου. Τήρης (TM Nam 6236) is a name confirmed in Trismegistos forty-one times for thirty-two individuals, in documents dating from 332 BC to AD 276 and originating from various parts of Egypt, but never from Pathyris.

Col. ii

1. The long dating formula of agoranomic contracts present in the discussed document is usually divided into four parts: the regnal date with the regnal year, the eponymous priesthoods of dynastic cults in Alexandria, the eponymous priesthoods of dynastic cults in Ptolemais, and the actual date with the month and the day (Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* [cit. n. 4], p. 247). The dating formula breaks in *P. Cair. Cat.* 10368 after the two first elements. However, they are sufficient to conclude that it is typical for Cleopatra III and Ptolemy IX Soter II (Lathyros), known from other documents written under the *agoranomos* Heliodoros. It is characteristic of the use of the term βασιλίσσης instead of Κλεοπάτρας, even if the last occurs sometimes in documents from this period, so the two are interchangeable and cannot be used for precise dating. Dating formula with the use of βασιλίσσης occurs only in documents from Pathyris written under Heliodoros or Sosos, whereas in documents from other places in Upper Egypt, like Diospolis Megale (*P. Stras.* II 81 [115 BC]) or Hermonthis (*UPZ* II 180 [113 BC]), written under other *agoranomoi* the term Κλεοπάτρας was always used.

2. ἱερείως for ἱερέως is customary in Pathyris, but not in the documents written in Krokodilopolis (Pestman, 'Agoranomoi' [cit. n. 5], p. 11; idem, 'A Greek tes-

tament from Pathyris (P. Lond. Inv. 2850)', *Journal of Egyptian Archaeology* 55 [1969], p. 138 *ad* l. 8). This points to Pathyris as the place of redaction of the discussed text. There are fifteen documents with this variation, noted by Vierros, *Bilingual Notaries* (cit. n. 5), p. 118 and n. 48, mostly in the documents of Heliodoros and Ammonios.

Ἀλεξάνδρῳ: The *omicron* is missing here. I have not found any other document from Pathyris with this kind of error. This word is additionally characterised by use of a 'flying *nu*' – it has the form of a hook with a raised leg, connected with the preceding *alpha*. The identical writing can be found in *P. Batav.* 6, ii, l. 2.

3. Φιλοπάτρων: A similar error can be found in *P. Strasb.* II 83 (Pathyris, 113 BC), l. 5: Φιλοπάτρος > Φιλοπατ(ο)ρος.

Aneta Skalec

La Sapienza University
 Faculty of Humanities
 Department of History, Anthropology,
 Religions, Art History, Media
 and Performing Arts
 Piazzale Aldo Moro, 5
 00185 Rome
 ITALY
 e-mail: anetaskalec@gmail.com

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UNIVERSITY OF WARSAW
FACULTY OF ARCHAEOLOGY
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UNIVERSITY OF WARSAW
FACULTY OF LAW AND ADMINISTRATION
CHAIR OF ROMAN LAW AND THE LAW OF ANTIQUITY

THE RAPHAEL TAUBENSCHLAG
FOUNDATION

THE JOURNAL OF JURISTIC PAPHYROLOGY

FOUNDED BY
RAPHAEL TAUBENSCHLAG

EDITED BY
TOMASZ DERDA
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JAKUB URBANIK

VOL. LII (2022)

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Computer design and DTP by
Piotr Berezowski, Tomasz Derda, Grzegorz Ochala, and Jakub Urbanik

Cover design by
Maryna Wiśniewska

Warszawa 2022

ISSN 0075–4277

This publication has been published with financial support
from the Faculty of Archaeology and Faculty of Law and Administration
of the University of Warsaw

Wydanie I (wersja pierwotna)

Nakład: 200 egz.

Druk i oprawa: Sowa Sp. z o.o., ul. Raszyńska 13, 05-500 Piaseczno

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Keywords: Greek papyri, Demotic papyri, Roman Egypt, Soknopaiou Nesos, account, wage labour, priests, temples, archives, Pakysis.

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Keywords: Christian (semi-)literary papyri, documentary papyri, dating.

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Keywords: Gebel Adda, Old Nubian, Christian Nubia, documentary sources, land sale, philology.

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Keywords: Dongola, Old Nubian, Christian Nubia, epigraphy, wall painting, philology.

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Keywords: *papa*, monasteries, monks, bishops, priests, titlature, monastic administration.

Juan P. LEWIS

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Abstract: This article proposes a correction to line 242 of papyrus *BGU V 1210*, the *Gnomon of the Idios Logos*. Substituting the accusative *οὐδικαρίους* for the dative *οὐδικαρίοις*, the *vicarii* of imperial slaves become objects of the infinitive *κθᾶσται* rather than the group to which the prohibition to buy things apply. Thus, instead of reading lines 241 and 242 separately, as it has traditionally been done, the two lines must be read together as two parts of a set of regulations. They limit the actions of imperial slaves, that is the *Καισαριανοὶ* of line 241, who are barred from buying goods auctioned off by the fiscus, purchasing *vicarii*, and marrying freedwomen. Read together, the two lines can be interpreted as a measure limiting imperial slaves' opportunities to increase their *peculium* by either taking advantage of the confiscation of private property by the fiscus or buying *vicarii*.

Keywords: *Gnomon*, imperial slaves, *vicarii*, public auctions, *bona damnatorum*, *SC Claudianum*.

Aneta SKALEC

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Abstract: The paper offers an edition of the agoranomic sale *P. Cair. Cat. 10368* originating from Pathyris and dated in 113 BC. Despite its fragmentary state of preservation, it provides interesting onomastic information and mentions a relatively rarely attested unit of measurement, *embadon*.

Keywords: Pathyris, Ptolemaic papyri, agoranomic contract, *embadon*, sale, Samios.

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Abstract: The article focuses on the attestations of clergy in the Oxyrhynchite archive of the Apion estate. In this group of texts, clerics feature in various roles such as administrators, cultivators, and legal specialists. A close reading of these documents within the context of normative sources and testimonies from outside the Apion archive allows us to come closer to an understanding of the clergy as a socially and economically diverse group poised to play intermediary roles in the networks of a great estate. The various aspects of the profiles of clerics recorded in the texts (wealth, education, skills, place of origin) encourage us to envisage the clerical status as an inter-

sectional experience where symbolic-religious and socio-economic factors remained in constant interplay.

Keywords: late antique clergy, Church history, Apion archive, great estates in Egypt, social status of the clergy.

Ewa WIPSYCKA

Bishops of the Patriarchate of Alexandria

travelling to meet their Patriarch in Late Antiquity and Early Middle Ages:

A study of the motives and duration of their journeys

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Abstract: The article considers the theme stated in the title in three separate sections focusing on three regions that were ecclesiastically subordinate to the patriarchate of Alexandria, that is Egypt, Libya Inferior and Pentapolis, and Nubia and Ethiopia. Bishops in the first area, strictly controlled by the patriarch, travelled to Alexandria first to be ordained and later to attend synods called by the patriarch and to conduct routine business, for example requesting financial assistance, waiting for a dispute between hierarchs to be solved, or in the case of breaking the discipline by the bishops or members of the clergy subordinate to them. Churches of Nubia and Ethiopia, located farther afar, sought the patriarch's attention almost exclusively in order to ordain bishops of the political centres of their states. The patriarch's ability to directly interfere with the internal matters of these distant Churches was very limited. For each of the examined regions, the author seeks to establish the approximate time required to travel to Alexandria. This section of the paper is based on antique and early medieval sources as well as post-medieval and nineteenth-century travel records.

Keywords: Adulis, Alwa, Aphou, Athanasius, Aksum, conditions of Nile navigation, *cursus publicus*, Darb al-Arba'in, Dongola, duration of travels on Nile, Frumentius, Longinus, Makuria, Nobadia, ordination of bishops for Ethiopia, Red Sea ports, synods in the Alexandrian patriarchate, travels across the Delta, Soba, Wadi Allaqi.

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A letter of Q. Aemilius Saturninus, praefectus Aegypti

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Abstract: The article is the first edition of an edict in the form of a letter from the prefect Q. Aemilius Saturninus (in office circa 197/8–200 CE) to the *strategi* of the Heptanomia and Arsinoites, copied on the back of a sheet cut from a land register attesting the *monartabos*-tax, probably from the Oxyrhynchites. The fragmentary edict, apparently in part a cover for a further letter

to a *beneficiarius*, mentions praiseworthy conduct by the latter in connection to a shortfall in the tax grain. A synthesis of the new text with other evidence for Saturninus as prefect is also presented.

Keywords: edict, official letter, prefect, *strategi*, *beneficiarius*, land register, *monartabos*.

DISCUSSION

Jerzy DANIELEWICZ

INΔIKTIΩN in editions of papyri and inscriptions:

A philologist's comment on the spelling and declension of the term 209

Abstract: The article points out misspellings of the word *INΔIKTIΩN* occurring in papyrological and epigraphic publications. Determining the correct spelling of the term entails conclusions regarding, more generally, the issue of editorial practices.

Keywords: indiction, Greek language, orthography, declension and accentuation, editorial conventions.

Joanne Vera STOLK

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Abstract: This article takes a 'bottom-up' approach to the spelling of the genitive case of the word *INΔIKTIΩN* as *INΔIKTIΩNΟΣ* or *INΔIKTIONΟΣ*. It is first shown that the editors of documentary papyri supplement this term in abbreviations and lacunae mostly with the *omicron* spelling. Chronological quantitative analysis shows that this is also the spelling that is used by ancient writers in contemporary documents. The conventional spelling in documentary papyri between the fourth and eighth centuries in Egypt may thus have differed from what is prescribed in literary sources.

Keywords: indiction, Greek language, orthography, editorial conventions, documentary papyrology.